

NDAC/LO/037

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REVIEW OF THE SET SOLUTION

by L Lindegren

1. Introduction

The process definition for the Set Solution (NDAC/LO/001) was written more than two years ago as the first in a series of definitions completed only last November. In the meantime, very significant developments have taken place in many areas having a more or less direct impact on the Set Solution. I would like to mention in particular

- the experience with full-scale, albeit still very simplified, set solutions at GI;
- the very complete and elegant data management structure developed at CUO/DSRI;
- the emergence and successful resolution of the slit ambiguity problem by removal of slit inconsistencies and the mesh method;
- the realization that some form of dynamical smoothing (DS) is indeed feasible and also very promising;
- a new approach to the attitude reconstitution (AR) initiated from RGO and partly motivated by the DS requirements, including redefinition of the attitude angles;
- theoretical developments, where Vectorial Astrometry provides an entirely new framework and a superb standard in notation and style.

In view of all this, the process definition and corresponding DID's (#1 - 8) must now be considered obsolete and superseded by the present review. The aspects of the set solution not covered by this review include data management, formation and solution of normals (including reordering), and elimination of slit inconsistencies, which all seem to be well in hand or covered by previous experiments.

2. Some preliminary definitions

I shall consistently use the indexing system in which the subscripts i , j , k and κ are reserved for identifying objects and instants (or intervals) of time, as explained below.

i = object number. Minor planets occupy a separate interval (e.g. $i > 90000000$) and are given a different object number for each crossing of the FOV.

k = frame number. This identifies a time interval of 2560 IDT samples or $32/15$ s (nominally, i.e. on the t scale).

κ = superframe number. This identifies a non-overlapping sequence of one or several adjacent frames. The number of frames in a superframe is in general variable. Since a frame can belong to at most one superframe, κ may be considered a discrete function of the frame number, $\kappa = \kappa(k)$, although there may be frames which belong to no superframe (e.g. immediately following a jet firing).

j = set number. This identifies a non-overlapping sequence of superframes in an interval of 6 - 12 h. $j = j(\kappa) = j(k)$.

The division of time into frames (if not the assignment of frame numbers) is done on board the satellite, whereas the division in superframes and sets is done by us.

The on-board clock defines a "nominal" time scale t , on which the IDT sample period is exactly $1/1200$ s, the gyro sampling period $16/15$ s, and the frame period $32/15$ s. This t may therefore be conveniently used for the SM and IDT preprocessings and the AR. By means of the datation provided with each telemetry format (5 frames), this can be related to the astronomical time scale

$$T = \text{seconds from J1988.0 TDT} = 1988 \text{ Jan } 1, 12 \text{ h TDT} \quad (1)$$

The nominal time is of no interest at the level of the set solution and later reductions, so it is appropriate to perform the time calibration at RGO and transfer T_k , the frame mid-time on the astronomical scale, along with the attitude data.

"Observations" generally form at the intersection of object space (i) with time (represented by k or j). Thus, from the point of view of the set solution, the observations are the grid coordinates $\bar{G}_{ik}^*$ of the different objects in a frame. The output of the set solution ("observations" for the Step 2/3 solution) are the mean abscissas $\bar{U}_{ij}$ of the different objects in the set. The grid coordinates refer to the frame mid-times (T_k) and the mean abscissas to the reference epoch of the object in the set (T_{ij}).

The superframe concept is motivated by the introduction of dynamical smoothing in the set solution. If $\Omega_k^{(AR)}$ is the attitude about the $\underline{z}$ axis as derived by the AR, then the "true" attitude used in the set solution is represented as a polynomial of degree N_Ω ,

$$\Omega_k = \Omega_k^{(AR)} + \sum_{\lambda=0}^{N_\Omega} (T_k - T_\kappa)^\lambda \Omega_{\kappa\lambda} = \Omega_k^{(AR)} + \underline{T}_{k-\kappa}' \underline{\Omega}_\kappa \quad (2)$$

where $\underline{T}_k$ and $\underline{\Omega}_\kappa$ are $(N_\Omega+1)$ -vectors. A geometrical set solution can be seen as the degenerate case of $N_\Omega = 0$ and $\kappa(k) = k$ (one superframe per frame). (T_κ is a suitable reference time for the superframe.) For DS, we may have $N_\Omega = 3$ and some 10 - 50 frames per superframe. In both cases, $\underline{\Omega}_\kappa$ are the unknowns to be determined by the set solution along with the mean abscissas ($\bar{U}_{ij}$) and large-scale distortion parameters ($\underline{d}_j$).

The spherical coordinates used in a set (abscissa, ordinate) refer to the triad $\underline{R}_j = [p_j \ q_j \ r_j]$. Its orientation with respect to the equatorial triad $\underline{n}$ is given by the three angles α_{rj} , δ_{rj} , and c_j according to the transformation

$$\underline{R}_j = \underline{n} \underline{A}_3(\alpha_{rj} + \frac{1}{2}\pi) \underline{A}_1(\frac{1}{2}\pi - \delta_{rj}) \underline{A}_3(c_j) \quad (3)$$

Until improved by the Step 2/3 solution, the set zero point correction c_j can be set identically zero. The choice of $\underline{R}_j$ can be made as soon as the set interval has been defined, e.g. by taking

$$\underline{r}_j = \langle \sum_{k \in j} \underline{z}_k \rangle, \quad \underline{p}_j = \langle \underline{n} \times \underline{r}_j \rangle, \quad \underline{q}_j = \underline{r}_j \times \underline{p}_j \quad (4)$$

where $\langle \rangle$ is the vector normalisation operator.

3. Input data from RGO

The data transferred on a weekly basis from the British side are:

(i) geocentric satellite ephemeris	0.01 Mbyte/week
(ii) star catalogue updates	1.0 Mbyte/week
(iii) attitude ephemeris (option A)	11 Mbyte/week
(iv) output from location estimator (incl photometry)	60 Mbyte/week
	total 72 Mbyte/week

With reasonable blocking, this should easily fit into two 1600 bpi tapes per week (79 % filling).

Geocentric satellite ephemeris. According to van der Ha (HST Meeting, 1984 May 23), the results of the a posteriori orbit determination will be given, for each 12 hour interval and each component of the position and velocity vectors, in the form (TBC)

$$x(T) = a_1 + a_2(T-T_0) + \sum_{r=1}^4 a_{r+2} \sin[r\omega(T-T_0) + a_{r+6}] \quad (5)$$

Here, $\omega = 7.292115... \cdot 10^{-5}$ is the (fixed) mean motion in geostationary orbit. It should be possible to get the coefficients in (5) and the reference epoch T_0 directly in equatorial J2000.0 coordinates and dynamical time (TDT), so that no additional transformation is required. The representation (5) thus requires 61 numbers (REAL*8) per 12 hour interval, or 6832 bytes/week.

Star catalogue updates. These are improved positions and colours from the attitude reconstitution and SM data processing (SMS update). In the course of a week, the motion of the z axis on the sky is about 30° , so that about 1/6 of the sky is covered. Therefore, some 15,000 - 20,000 programme stars are observed and most of them may be subject to the SMS updating. The data per star could be as follows:

- star ID number	INTEGER*4
- α, δ (or $\Delta\alpha, \Delta\delta$ wrt INCA position?)	} 7 x REAL*4
- $\sigma_\alpha, \sigma_\delta, \rho$	
- B-V, σ_{B-V}	

i.e. 32 bytes/star. This would give some 0.7 Mbyte/week. (If α, δ is preferred to $\Delta\alpha, \Delta\delta$, then double precision may be necessary.)

Attitude ephemeris. The attitude is defined in terms of the heliotropic angles (ξ, ν, Ω) replacing the old $(\alpha_z, \delta_z, \omega)$, see Lindegren (1984 April 17).

As to the form in which the attitude ephemeris is transferred, there are however two options:

- (A) the attitude angles are explicitly given for every frame;
- (B) the spline coefficients etc are given for suitable intervals (e.g. between jet firings).

Option B would give perhaps a factor 10 smaller data volume. This is however not a real advantage in the weekly data transfer, since it would not reduce the number of tapes. A serious disadvantage of this option is, on the other hand, that the format is much more complicated than in option A, especially if it must be flexible enough to permit different kinds of analytical representations (e.g. pure spline versus harmonics + spline, with a varying number of terms of different kinds). Insofar as the data volume is not prohibitive, I would strongly recommend option A as being by far the simplest interface.

The attitude file will then contain the following for each frame (k):

- frame ID number (k)	INTEGER*4
- frame mid-time (T_k)	REAL*8
- heliotropic angles $\xi_k, \nu_k, \Omega_k^{(AR)}$	3 x REAL*8

i.e. 36 bytes/frame or 10.206 Mbyte/week.

Output from location estimator. The contents of this file will be roughly the following for each frame:

- frame ID number (k)	INTEGER*4	
- number of stars in the frame (NSTAR)	INTEGER*4	
-- object ID number (signed)	INTEGER*4	} NSTAR times
-- $\bar{G}^*$	REAL*8	
-- $\sigma_{\bar{G}}^*, \Delta \bar{G}, \sigma_{\hat{G}}, \pm GOF$	4 x REAL*4	
-- $A^*, \sigma_{A^*}, \hat{A}, \sigma_{\hat{A}}, B$	5 x REAL*4	

Since NSTAR = 4 on the average, we have some 200 bytes/frame or 56.7 Mbytes per week. The sign on the object ID number indicates preceding (+) or following (-) field; the sign on the GOF indicates whether the observation was used for the OTF calibration (+) or not (-).

4. Calculation of the grid coordinate from current parameter values

This procedure is central to the set solution, in that it is precisely the difference between the observed grid coordinate ($\bar{G}_{ik}^*$, from RGO) and the computed value ($\bar{G}_{ik}$) that drives the least-squares adjustment. [The barred $\bar{G}$ is the "smoothed" grid coordinate, i.e. excluding small-scale distortion.]

$\bar{G}_{ik}$ is completely determined by the frame mid-time (T_k), the object's proper direction ($\underline{u}_{ik}$) and the attitude angles (ξ_k, ν_k, Ω_k) at this instant, and the large-scale distortion pertaining to the set ($\underline{d}_j$).

The set solution generates successively updated values for the unknowns, which are the mean abscissas ($\bar{u}_{ij}$), the attitude corrections (Ω_k), and the large-scale distortion ($\underline{d}_j$). Initially, $\bar{u}_{ij}$ are calculated from astrometric data in the current object catalogue (astrometric parameters for stars, orbital parameters for minor planets), Ω_k is set to zero, and $\underline{d}_j$ taken from previous sets. The initial calculation of proper direction is similarly made from current catalogue parameters only. However, after the first updating of the mean abscissa, $\bar{u}_{ij}$ contains new information not in the current catalogue, and must therefore be fully taken into account in subsequent calculations of $\underline{u}_{ik}$ and $\bar{G}_{ik}$. A procedure for this was proposed by me earlier (NDAC/LO/016), but this is not quite satisfactory. A better method will be given below [eqn (8)].

It is recalled that the mean abscissa of object i in set j ($\bar{u}_{ij}$) corresponds to the coordinate direction ($\underline{u}_{ij}$) to the object at a reference epoch T_{ij} close to the mean epoch of observation in the set for this particular object.

The input list for calculating $\bar{G}_{ik}$ is organized according to the categories defined by the subscripts.

Input per object

i = object number
 $\underline{a}_i$ = astrometric or orbital parameters
 C_i = $(B-V) - 0.5$ = colour

Input per set

j = set number
 $\underline{R}_j$ = [$\underline{p}_j$ $\underline{q}_j$ $\underline{r}_j$] = set triad
 $\underline{d}_j$ = $\{g_{jmn}, g'_{jmn}, h_{jmn}, h'_{jmn}\}$ = large-scale distortion coefficients

Input per superframe

κ = superframe number
 T_{κ} = superframe reference time
 $\bar{\Omega}_{\kappa}$ = attitude correction parameters

Input per frame

k = frame number
 T_k = frame mid-time
 $\epsilon_k, \nu_k, \Omega_k^{(AR)}$ = heliotropic attitude angles from the AR

Input per abscissa

ij = abscissa number (for object i in set j)
 T_{ij} = abscissa reference time
 $\bar{v}_{ij}$ = (mean) abscissa

Input per grid coordinate (not strictly necessary)

ik = grid coordinate number (for object i in frame k)
 f_{ik} = field index (+1 for preceding, -1 for following field)

Output per grid coordinate

ik = grid coordinate number (for object i in frame k)
 $\bar{G}_{ik}$ = smoothed grid coordinate

Procedure

P1. For each frame, calculate the auxiliary triad

$$\bar{e}_k = [e_{1k} \ e_{2k} \ z_k] = K \ A_3[\lambda_s(T_k)] \ A_1(\nu_k - \frac{1}{2}\pi) \ A_2(\frac{1}{2}\pi - \epsilon_k) \quad (6)$$

and, if $N_{\Omega} > 0$, the time difference $\tau_k = T_k - T_{\kappa}$ needed in eqn (2).

P2. For each abscissa, calculate from $\underline{a}_i$ the catalogue coordinate direction $\bar{u}_{ij}^{(cat)}$ at time T_{ij} and hence the catalogue abscissa

$$\bar{v}_{ij}^{(cat)} = \text{ATAN2} \left(q_{j-ij}^{(cat)}, p_{j-ij}^{(cat)} \right) \quad (7)$$

P3. For each grid coordinate, calculate from $\underline{a}_i$ the catalogue proper direction at time T_k , $\bar{u}_{ik}^{(cat)}$.

Procedures P1 - P3 need only be carried out once per set (provided the results can be stored), since they are independent of the adjusted parameters.

P4. To get the grid coordinate, calculate first a proper direction consistent with the current abscissa estimate, by rotating away from the catalogue proper direction by a small angle corresponding to the abscissa difference:

$$\underline{u}_{ik} = \underline{u}_{ik}^{(cat)} + (\underline{r}_j \times \underline{u}_{ik}^{(cat)}) [\bar{v}_{ij} - \bar{v}_{ij}^{(cat)}] \quad (8)$$

The abscissa difference (in brackets) must be small, up to a few arcseconds, in order to preserve unit length of $\underline{u}_{ik}$. It may require adjustment by $\pm 2\pi$. The field coordinates (w_{ik} , z_{ik}) are then obtained as

$$w_{ik} = - (e'_{1k} \underline{u}_{ik}) \sin(\Omega_k + \frac{1}{2} f_{ik} \gamma) + (e'_{2k} \underline{u}_{ik}) \cos(\Omega_k + \frac{1}{2} f_{ik} \gamma) \quad (9)$$

$$z_{ik} = z'_{k-ik} \quad (10)$$

with Ω_k from (2). [The direction cosines (w , z) replace the former field angles (η , ζ) in the definition of $\underline{d}_j$.] Finally,

$$\bar{G}_{ik} = \sum_m \sum_n \left[(g_{jmn} + C_i \bar{g}_{jmn}) + f_{ik} (h_{jmn} + C_i \bar{h}_{jmn}) \right] w_{ik}^m z_{ik}^n \quad (11)$$

The sums are taken from $m = n = 0$ to N_d for the achromatic distortion terms (g_{jmn} , h_{jmn}) and to $N'_d \leq N_d$ for the chromaticity terms ($\bar{g}_{jmn}$, $\bar{h}_{jmn}$). In order to define the origin of w , however, we put

$$g_{j00} = \bar{g}_{j00} = 0 \quad (12)$$

(Lindgren, 1984 April 30). The number of distortion parameters is

$$\dim(\underline{d}_j) = [(N_d+1)(N_d+2) - 1] + \max[0, (N'_d+1)(N'_d+2) - 1] \quad (13)$$

(in which $N'_d < 0$ if there are no chromaticity terms).

NOTE: Although P4 is here described as a complete routine, we shall see that it should be combined with the calculation of partial derivatives for the observation equation.

5. Observation equation; partial derivatives

The observation equation for object i in frame k is

$$\frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial \bar{v}_{ij}} \Delta \bar{v}_{ij} + \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial \Omega'_k} \Delta \Omega'_k + \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial \underline{d}_j} \Delta \underline{d}_j + \text{noise} = \bar{G}_{ik}^* - \bar{G}_{ik} + \text{integer} \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta \bar{v}_{ij}$, $\Delta \Omega'_k$, and $\Delta \underline{d}_j$ are the adjustments to the unknowns in the next iteration. As already mentioned, the initial values for the unknowns are

$$\bar{v}_{ij} = \bar{v}_{ij}^{\text{(cat)}}, \quad \Omega'_k = 0, \quad \underline{d}_j = \underline{d}_{j-1} \quad (\text{e.g.}) \quad (15)$$

The rigorous development of the partial derivatives is quite straightforward. From (11) we have immediately the derivatives with respect to the distortion parameters ($\underline{d}_j$),

$$\frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial g_{jmn}} = w_{ik}^m z_{ik}^n \quad \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial g_{jmn}^-} = C_i w_{ik}^m z_{ik}^n \quad (16a,b)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial h_{jmn}} = f_{ik} w_{ik}^m z_{ik}^n \quad \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial h_{jmn}^-} = f_{ik} C_i w_{ik}^m z_{ik}^n \quad (16c,d)$$

From (11) we also have

$$\frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial w_{ik}} = \sum_m \sum_n \left[(g_{jmn} + C_i g_{jmn}^-) + f_{ik} (h_{jmn} + C_i h_{jmn}^-) \right] m w_{ik}^{m-1} z_{ik}^n \quad (17a)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial z_{ik}} = \sum_m \sum_n \left[(g_{jmn} + C_i g_{jmn}^-) + f_{ik} (h_{jmn} + C_i h_{jmn}^-) \right] n w_{ik}^m z_{ik}^{n-1} \quad (17b)$$

in which it may be permissible to skip the chromaticity and/or higher-order terms, depending on their actual size. Then, using (2) and (9) - (10),

$$\frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial \Omega'_k} = \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial \Omega_k} \frac{\partial \Omega_k}{\partial \Omega'_k} = \left(\frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial w_{ik}} \frac{\partial w_{ik}}{\partial \Omega_k} + \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial z_{ik}} \frac{\partial z_{ik}}{\partial \Omega_k} \right) \frac{\partial \Omega_k}{\partial \Omega'_k} \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial \Omega'_k} = - \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial w_{ik}} \left[(e'_{1k} u_{ik}) \cos(\Omega_k + \frac{1}{2} f_{ik} \gamma) + (e'_{2k} u_{ik}) \sin(\Omega_k + \frac{1}{2} f_{ik} \gamma) \right] \underline{r}'_k \quad (19)$$

For the derivative with respect to the mean abscissa, we have from (8) - (10),

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial \bar{v}_{ij}} &= \left(\frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial w_{ik}} \frac{\partial w_{ik}}{\partial u'_{ik}} + \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial z_{ik}} \frac{\partial z_{ik}}{\partial u'_{ik}} \right) \frac{\partial u_{ik}}{\partial \bar{v}_{ij}} \\ &= \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial w_{ik}} \left(-\sin(\Omega_k + \frac{1}{2} f_{ik} \gamma) e'_{1k} + \cos(\Omega_k + \frac{1}{2} f_{ik} \gamma) e'_{2k} \right) (\underline{r}_j \times \underline{u}_{ij}^{(cat)}) + \\ &\quad + \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial z_{ik}} z'_k (\underline{r}_j \times \underline{u}_{ik}^{(cat)}) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

With

$$\underline{\Delta}_{ik} = \begin{bmatrix} - \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial w_{ik}} \sin(\Omega_k + \frac{1}{2} f_{ik} \gamma) \\ \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial w_{ik}} \cos(\Omega_k + \frac{1}{2} f_{ik} \gamma) \\ \frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial z_{ik}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

we have more compactly,

$$\frac{\partial \bar{G}_{ik}}{\partial \bar{v}_{ij}} = \underline{\Delta}'_{ik} (\underline{E}_k \times \underline{r}_j)' \underline{u}_{ik}^{(cat)} \quad (22)$$

in which only $\underline{\Delta}_{ik}$ is subject to updating and $(\underline{E}_k \times \underline{r}_j)$ moreover is the same for the different observations in a frame.